

Effect of Client Size Determinants on Audit Report Lag in Money Deposit Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the effect of client size on audit report lag in money deposit banks in Nigeria. The study adopted explanatory research design. The population of the study comprised of some selected Deposit money banks, out of which some are selected as a case study for the period from 2010 to 2021. Secondary data was sourced from the annual reports of the Web pages of selected Deposit money Banks in Nigeria including books, journals, and articles. Data was analyzed using Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Linear regression technique as well as E-views. Findings revealed that only client size and external auditor type had significant effect on audit report lag while other variables like auditor's size, board size, and board meetings were not significant drivers of audit report lag. Therefore, total assets cause delay in audit reports while external auditor size help to reduce the audit report lag. This implies that the larger the total assets that client has, the more will delay in audit report lag that will be experienced by the Bank. The study therefore recommended that banks and audit firms should leverage efficient audit processes used with larger clients to optimize the audit process for smaller clients; banks should be encouraged to adopt governance practices that include frequent and well-organized board meetings by establishing governance frameworks that set minimum standards for board engagement and oversight to ensure more efficient audit processes.

Keywords: Audit report Lag, Client size, Deposit money banks, Nigeria

Word Counts: 233

Introduction

An external audit determines if the company's financial records system conforms to the internationally recognized accounting standards; and if any detected inaccuracies in the records, if present, are simply recording mistakes or indications of misappropriation and/or fraudulent actions by the company's employees. In essence, it guarantees the dependability and precision of the financial figures that are being presented. External audit reports, which are created annually as a statutory audit of a firm, offer stakeholders essential information to support their policy decisions and to evaluate the effectiveness of the organization. Thus, the need of external audit reports cannot be overstated, since poor quality audits can be deceptive and lead to investors misallocating of resources.

Furthermore, an audit is highly regarded as a method of enhancing the financial information utilized by managers in the process of making decisions. An auditor can enhance the quality of the input data by identifying inaccuracies and by promoting greater diligence among employees in record preparation. Greater precision of data will enhance internal decision-making. The utilization of more precise data from external sources for credit and investment research, labour negotiations, or regulatory choices will enhance the effectiveness of managers. At the conclusion of a financial accounting year, the management of a corporate entity is required to compile its financial statements, a practice known as stewardship accounting, for sharing with stakeholders. Consequently, these financial statements undergo an external audit conducted by a certified auditor who performs an Audit procedure and provides their assessment on the accuracy and impartiality of the submitted financial statements. Nevertheless, this entire procedure requires several days or even months from the moment management compiles the financial statements until the audit occurs. Audit report lag refers to the duration between the preparation of financial statements and the signing of the audit report.

Financial statements are compiled by directors and issued with a date at the conclusion of the fiscal year. Nevertheless, the public release of these financial statements hinges on the certification of independent auditors. Prior to finalising a report on the financial accounts, auditors or audit firms thoroughly scrutinise the books and undertake other essential procedures. An audit report lag is the time interval between the conclusion of the financial year and the date when the audit report is issued (Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018; Egbunike & Asuzu, 2022). Ezat (2015) defined an audit report lag as the time span between the closing date of the balance sheet and the date the audit report is signed. This refers to how long it takes for the audit report to be finalized. Audit report lag highlights a key attribute of accounting information, which is timeliness. According to Usman (2014) he noted that the timely release of a company's financial information heavily depends on the time taken to complete the audit since financial statements cannot be issued until the audit is finished. It is important to remember that accounting information is only useful when it is timely. In other words, if the reports cannot assist users in making decisions, they lose their relevance. Ideally, companies should aim to reduce audit lag to improve market efficiency Abdullah., Raweh, Kamardi & Malik, 2019; Oyedokun, 2019). Ahmed and Hossain (2010) reported that shorter audit report lags enhance the value derived from audited annual reports.

Excessive delays in audit reports can compromise the quality of financial statements. When the auditor's opinion on the accuracy and fairness of financial statements is not disclosed promptly, it can worsen information asymmetry within the firm and diminish investor confidence. The demand for high-quality, timely financial reporting has grown globally, driven by increasing globalization in business and capital markets (Dibia & Onwuchekwe, 2013). In certain countries, regulations have been introduced to promote the timeliness of financial reports. For instance, the US Securities and Exchange Commission (US SEC) mandates that annual audited financial statements must be released within 90 days of the fiscal year-end, while quarterly reports must be prepared within 45 days. In the UK, regulations set different deadlines based on market capitalization. Companies with a market value below \$75 million are required to file within 90 days, those between \$75 million and \$700 million within 75 days, and firms with over \$700 million in market value must file within 60 days of the fiscal year's close.

In Turkey, the filing requirement is 70 days. In Nigeria, public companies are mandated by the Companies and Allied Matters Act of 2020 (CAMA, 2020) to present audited annual financial

statements to shareholders no later than 180 days (6 months) after the fiscal year ends (Oladipupo & Ilaboya, 2013). All companies should strive to reduce the audit lag to improve both market efficiency and client size. A shorter interval between the fiscal year-end and the release of financial statements leads to greater benefits from audited annual reports (Adzrin, Ahmad & Kamarudin, 2014; Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019).

Thus, providing timely information is a critical aspect of delivering value-relevant financial reports. The relevance of accounting information largely depends on its availability when needed for decision-making. Timeliness, like materiality, influences various qualitative factors, such as faithful representation and reliability, which are essential for decision-making. Information must reach decision-makers before it loses its capacity to influence their choices. The sooner the relevant information is made available to users the more it has its capacity to influence decisions. Lack of timeliness can deprive the information of its usefulness.

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of Client Size Determinants (Board size, audit committee, Board meetings, financial year end and date of the audit report) on Audit report lag using some Deposit Money Banks as case study.

Literature Review

Audit Report Lag (ARL)

The audit report lag refers to the period between the end of a company's financial year and the submission of its audited financial statements by external auditors. It represents the time auditors take to complete their audit of the financial statements prepared by the company's management. Dibia and Onwuchekwe (2013) defines audit report lag as the interval between the year-end, the preparation of financial statements, and the issuance of the audit report. The term is also used to describe the time that passes from the close of the fiscal year to the completion of audit fieldwork. This stage is typically marked by the end of substantive audit tests, when the auditor leaves the client's premises and signs the audit report (Tany, Raghunandan & Barua, 2011; Bemby, Abulosin, & Mursidi, 2013; Enofe, Mgbame, & Abadua, 2013; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024).

Al-Ajmi (2008) affirmed that audit lag is crucial as it directly impacts the timeliness of accounting information. Timeliness in corporate reporting involves three distinct periods: the audit lag period, the interim period, and the overall reporting lag. These three periods together cover the total time between the company's financial year-end and when its financial statements are presented to shareholders or filed with the relevant authorities (Akhalumeh, Izevbekhai & Ohenhen, 2017).

Client Size

According to Akhalumeh, Izevbekhai and Ohenhen (2017) client size is commonly determined by the total assets, which represent the combined book value of all assets owned by an individual, company, or organization. This metric is frequently used in evaluating net worth within debt covenants. The total asset value is calculated after accounting for depreciation. Net worth, in its simplest form, is the difference between total assets and total liabilities. In a corporate setting, total assets are the resources a company owns that have economic value and are expected to provide future benefits. These assets are listed on the company's balance sheet.

Assets are categorized by liquidity: liquid assets, which can be quickly converted into cash, and illiquid assets, which are not as easily sold for cash. On the balance sheet, assets are further divided into current and long-term. Current assets are expected to be liquidated within one year, while long-term assets take more than a year to convert into cash. Assets, as items of economic value, are used over time to generate benefits for their owner. In the case of a business, these assets are recorded in accounting books and reflected in the company's balance sheet. Common categories include cash, marketable securities, accounts receivable, prepaid expenses, inventory, fixed assets, intangible assets, goodwill, and other assets. Depending on the relevant accounting standards, the assets that make up total assets may or may not be listed at their current market values. International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) tend to allow assets to be listed at current market values, while Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) are generally more restrictive in allowing such adjustments (Fagbemi & Uadiale, 2011).

Board Size

Board size refers to the total number of directors on the board of each sample firm which is inclusive of the CEO and Chairman for each accounting year. This will include outside directors, executive directors and non-executive directors. It is the governing body of a company, elected by shareholders in the case of public companies to set strategy and oversee management. The board typically meets at regular intervals. Every public company must have a board of directors (Ahmed & Che-Ahmad 2016; Oyedokun, & Balogun, 2022). Some private companies and nonprofit organizations also have a board of directors. The board makes key decisions on issues such as mergers and dividends, hires senior managers, and sets their pay. The CBN Code prescribes a minimum and maximum board size of five and twenty directors respectively. The SEC Code prescribes a minimum of five directors and directs that the board of a company be of sufficient size relative to the scale and complexity of the operations of the company. The board of directors' candidates can be nominated by the company's nominations committee or by outsiders seeking change. They are responsible for helping a corporation set broad goals, supporting senior management in pursuit of those goals, and ensuring the company has adequate, well-managed resources at its disposal. The board of directors typically includes the chief executive officer and sometimes other senior managers, alongside board members not otherwise affiliated with the company (Ahmed & Che-Ahmad, 2016; Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020). Zemzem and Ftouhi (2013) defined an inside director as a company employee, though the category sometimes also covers significant shareholders. Independent, or outside, directors are only involved with the company through their board membership. Independent directors face fewer conflicts of interest than company insiders in discharging their fiduciary obligations.

Audit Committee Size

The length of time that passes between the conclusion of a company's fiscal year and the release of its audited financial statements is known as the audit report lag, and it is impacted by a number of variables, including the audit committee's size. A company's audit committee, which is a subcommittee of the board of directors, is essential to managing the financial reporting procedure and communicating with outside auditors. An understanding of the intersection between governance structures and corporate characteristics can be gained by analyzing the relationship between audit committee size and client size in the context of audit report lag.

Auditors can be classified into internal, external and forensic. An internal auditor works for the entity which he or her audits. This person conducts independent analyses of a variety of processes within a business and may also evaluate the level of corporate governance. Internal auditors report their findings to the board of directors, along with remediation suggestions. An external auditor is independent of the clients which he or she audits. An external auditor may be certified by a state agency to be a certified public accountant, and thus allowed to issue certified reports on the financial condition of clients. An external auditor may instead work for a government, and in that role is tasked with examining the records of individuals and businesses to see if they have complied with the various tax laws. A forensic auditor investigates whether fraud has been committed. The resulting evidence is used to prosecute the party that committed fraud. A forensic auditor may be employed within a business or may work for an outside firm that conducts these investigations for its clients. The size of auditors is very important for the success of an organization (Baatwah, Salleh & Stewart, 2019).

Board Meeting

A board meeting is a meeting of the board of directors that sets the policy and strategic direction for a corporation, publicly traded company, government body or non-profit. A board meeting is being held to review the strategic plan that has been developed by the board of directors. The goal is for the directors to agree on which direction to move in and how it will be implemented. Simply put, a board meeting is a meeting to set policy and strategy (Ahmed & Che-Ahmad, 2016). Board meetings can vary depending on how mature a company is. Start-ups and tech companies sometimes favor a more pragmatic approach, while larger corporations typically follow strict guidelines meant to help provide order and structure. Still, many of the components of these board meetings remain very similar (Ahmed & Che-Ahmad, 2016; Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020).

In the opinion of Shaikh Ali (2011) before a board meeting begins, a document is circulated, consisting of a report by each director itemizing anything that needs attention and their value judgments concerning various issues. When the board meeting begins, a person, usually the CEO of the company, presents an overview of how well their goals are being met and any issues that need to be addressed. Directors may present on their sections as well, or merely be present to answer questions if the report was sufficient. Following this, a member of the board will raise topics that they feel need addressing or comment on progress toward various goals. The board chair will then elicit discussion by seeking comments on what was presented and taking action on any issues that come up. The board may wish to have a discussion without the CEO or other leaders present, in order to assess their performance. Sometimes other procedural motions are required before the meeting is adjourned, such as certifying stock option grants (Ahmed & Che-Ahmad, 2016).

External Auditor Type

The audit report lag refers to the time that elapses between a company's fiscal year-end and the issuance of its audited financial statements. It is a crucial metric that can be influenced by various factors, including the type of auditor engaged by the company. Auditors play a pivotal role in

ensuring the accuracy and reliability of financial statements, and their characteristics can significantly impact the duration of the audit process and, consequently, the audit report lag.

An external auditor performs an audit in accordance with specific laws, statutes or rules, of the financial statements of a company, government entity, other legal entity, or organization, and is independent of the entity being audited. External auditors can also be called statutory auditors, this is because both external auditors and statutory auditors are both authorized and governed by law or a statute. Users of these entities' financial information, such as investors, government agencies, and the general public, rely on the external auditor to present an unbiased and independent audit report (Shaikh Ali, 2011; Ogundajo, Odunayo, Osunsusi, Desi, & Oyedokun, 2023). An external audit, defined as a company audit which is performed by a party which is not a department or employed by business to be audited, is very commonly performed. The external audit approach has two main purposes. The company believes an outside party will be more efficient at work or because of a governmental entity (Oyedokun, Okwuosa, & Isah, 2019; ICAEW, 2011).

ICAEW (2011) opined that the manner of appointment, the qualifications, and the format of reporting by an external auditor are defined by statute, which varies according to jurisdiction. External auditors must be members of one of the recognized professional accountancy bodies. External auditors normally address their reports to the shareholders of a corporation. The objective of the external audit includes the determination of the completeness and accuracy of the accounting records of the client, to ensure that the records of the clients are prepared as per the accounting framework which applies to them and to ensure that the financial statements of the client present the true and fair results and the financial position. The main responsibility is to verify the general ledger of the company and make all other essential inquiries from the management of the company. It helps to determine the real picture of the company's market situation and the financial situation, which further provides the basis for managerial decisions.

Policeman Theory

This had immense popularity and widespread acceptance until the 1940s. The concept of the policeman posits that the auditor, being a policeman, should prioritize the arithmetical precision of financial data and accounting records. Therefore, it anticipates that the auditor will proactively identify and prevent fraudulent activities, which is once again the contention supported by users of financial statements. Nevertheless, it implies that auditors serve as vigilant overseers, rather than relentless detectives.

Clearly, based on the theoretical arguments, it is evident that the majority of professionals support the idea of auditing that combines the functions of being a vigilant overseer and a diligent investigator. Audit is a societal construct, and its ongoing significance is contingent upon fulfilling society's expectations. Thus, it is incumbent upon the audit professional to relinquish his old position and accept the broader role that emerges from society expectations. As society is inherently dynamic rather than static, the function of audit cannot be limited to its conventional definition. The nature of human economic transactions is undergoing a transformation, evidently leading to an increase in human avarice, therefore undermining the long-standing beliefs in morality and satisfaction. This behaviour driven by avarice is resulting in rudimentary acquisition and so-called intelligent behaviors inside a globalised framework of personal acquisition. Societal respect in human social interactions is progressively shaped by wealth, and even the strength of

nations is determined by economic power. This creates a conducive environment for so-called smart wealth acquisition methods that frequently disregard moral standards and even national legislation (Tiamiyu, & Oyedokun, 2019; Ogoun, & Odogu, 2020).

The theory further posits that the auditor bears the responsibility of actively seeking, uncovering, and thwarting any instances of fraudulent conduct. Nevertheless, the primary responsibility of auditors is to offer a decent level of confidence and remain impartial, accurate, and unbiased assessment of the financial statements. Nevertheless, auditors have under increased pressure to identify fraudulent activities following recent reporting scandals. In contemporary societies, it might be contended that the consumers of statements expect auditors to assume the responsibility of detecting fraud, as they rely on audit reports for analysis and decision-making. However, auditors are not obligated to uncover all instances of fraud but should enhance their ability to identify fraudulent activities in order to inspire public trust. The management and governance of an organization have the main responsibility for fraud prevention and detection. It is therefore crucial to prioritize the prevention of fraud. Nonetheless, the auditor is also obligated to give proper consideration to the end consumers of audit reports and should take into account the potential for significant errors caused by fraudulent activities while assessing audit risk.

Empirical Review

Bamber, Bamber and Schoderbek (1993) explored the relationship between audit report lag (ARL) and client size, among other factors. Previous research indicates that audit delays increase with the complexity of the audit work, decrease with stronger incentives for timely reporting, and rise with the extent to which auditors use a structured approach to auditing. Kinney and McDaniel (1993) revealed that audit delays are longer for firms with interim earnings overstatements and declining earnings, and that these delays are more pronounced with larger overstatements of interim earnings.

Jaggi, and Tsui (1999) examined the association between audit report lag (ARL) and factors such as auditor business risk and audit firm technology in Hong Kong. This study, which analyzed data from 393 Hong Kong companies over the period from 1991 to 1993, used financial condition and family ownership/control as proxies for auditor business risk, and the structured versus unstructured audit approach as a proxy for audit firm technology. Other control variables included the number of subsidiaries, the nature of the client's business, company size, unexpected positive earnings news, and the nature of the audit opinion. The regression analysis found a positive correlation between audit report lag and the financial risk index, indicating that companies with poorer financial conditions experience longer audit delays. The study also found that companies audited by firms using a structured audit approach have longer audit delays. The relationship between ARL and family ownership/control suggested that family-owned or controlled companies might experience shorter audit delays, although these results were not statistically significant. Larger companies were associated with shorter audit delays.

In a related study, Chan, Lin and Mo (2006) investigated how political and economic factors in China affect the timeliness of audit opinions. This research revealed that audit firms operating exclusively within China are more susceptible to political pressure from government agencies. Conversely, firms with international operations tend to provide more accurate reports on state-owned enterprises and agencies to mitigate potential financial risks. The study also found that

companies receiving negative audit opinions (qualified reports) are more likely to switch from international to local auditors, unlike those receiving positive opinions (unqualified reports).

Abdullah (2007) assessed how the composition of the board of directors, the audit committee, and the separation of the roles of board chairman and CEO influence audit report lag in Malaysia. The findings highlighted that board independence, and the separation of the chairman and CEO roles are significantly associated with audit report lag. The study also found a positive correlation between audit report lag and leverage, while profitability showed a negative relationship with audit report lag.

Ezat, and El-Masry (2008) explored the main factors influencing the timeliness of corporate internet reporting among Egyptian companies listed on the Cairo and Alexandria Stock Exchange. The study identified significant correlations between reporting timeliness and several factors, including firm size, industry type, liquidity, ownership structure, board composition, and board size. It was found that larger firms in the service sector with higher liquidity, a greater proportion of independent directors, more board members, and a larger free float tend to disclose information on their websites more promptly. Additionally, the study observed a notable relationship between these variables and various aspects of reporting timeliness.

Lee and Jahng (2008) examined the determinants of audit report lag (ARL) with a focus on auditor-related factors. ARL is crucial as it impacts the timing of earnings announcements, which in turn affects the promptness of earnings releases. This research, using a recent sample from Korea, found that ARL is negatively correlated with non-audit fees paid to auditors, suggesting a "knowledge spillover" effect from non-audit services. Additionally, ARL was found to be negatively associated with the use of Big 4 auditors and unqualified audit opinions. However, the study did not find significant relationships between ARL and auditor tenure or abnormal audit fees. Further analysis indicated that abnormal audit hours and the provision of tax services, along with internal control system design services, significantly reduce ARL.

Afify (2009) investigated the factors influencing audit report lag (ARL) in Egypt. This research introduced new explanatory variables related to corporate governance (CG) characteristics—such as board independence, CEO duality, and the presence of an audit committee—that had not been examined before. The ARL for the 85 sampled listed companies ranged from a minimum of 19 days to a maximum of 115 days, with an average lag of about two months. The regression analysis revealed that board independence, CEO duality, and the existence of an audit committee significantly impact ARL. In contrast, ownership concentration did not significantly affect ARL. Additionally, three control variables—company size, industry, and profitability—were found to have a significant effect on ARL. The adjusted R^2 indicated that 57.10% of the variation in ARL could be explained by these independent variables.

Ilaboya and Christian (2014) assessed the impact of corporate governance on audit report lag in Nigeria, focusing on the size of the board, audit committee independence, and audit firm size. Utilizing time series and cross-sectional data from 2007-2011, the study examined 40 manufacturing companies from a total of 120 listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The analysis, which employed descriptive statistics, correlation, and Ordinary Least Squares regression, found that board size, audit firm quality, and firm size significantly influenced audit report lag. However, the objectivity of the board and the number of audit committee members did not have a major impact on the timing of the annual audit report release.

Adzrin, Ahmad and Kamarudin (2014) explored the factors influencing annual audit lag in Malaysia, analyzing data from approximately 100 registered firms listed on the Kuala Lumpur Stock Exchange between 1996 and 2000. The study tested eight hypotheses related to audit delay, including factors such as company size, sector, income level, presence of unusual items, audit opinion type, auditor level, accounting period end, and risk level. The findings indicated that audit report delays are notably longer for firms with accounting years ending on dates other than December 31, those receiving qualified opinions, non-financial sector companies, firms not audited by Big Five firms, companies with negative earnings, and those with higher risks.

Methodology

The study adopted explanatory research design to explain ideas and opinions on audit report lag and its relationship with the client size and other sub-variables. The population of the study comprised of some selected Deposit money banks, out of which some are selected as a case study for the period from 2010 to 2021. Secondary data was sourced from the annual reports of the Web pages of selected Deposit money Banks in Nigeria including books, journals, and articles. Data was analyzed using Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Linear regression technique as well as E-views.

Presentation of Data

Table 1 shows the Descriptive Analysis

Statistic	Audit report lag	Client's size	Total asset (₦billion)	Board size	External auditor type	Board meetings
Nbr. of observations	80	80	80	80	80	80
Minimum	15.000	3.000	0.014	5.000	0.000	1.000
Maximum	344.000	7.000	8932.373	22.000	1.000	13.000
Mean	75.104	6.000	1326.932	14.039	0.963	6.000
Variance (n-1)	1964.147	0.320	4088138.147	12.327	0.037	4.907
Standard deviation (n-1)	44.319	0.566	2021.914	3.511	0.191	2.215

The audit report typically takes about 75 days to issue, but this varies widely, with some taking as little as 15 days and others up to 344 days. Client sizes are relatively similar, averaging around 6, with a narrow range from 3 to 7, suggesting a consistent clientele base. However, total assets show significant differences, with mean total assets at 1327 billion Naira but ranging from 0.014 to 8932.373 billion Naira, indicating a wide financial disparity among entities. Board sizes vary, averaging around 14 members with a range from 5 to 22, suggesting diverse governance structures. Most entities use the same type of external auditor, suggesting potential standardization in auditor selection practices. On average, entities hold six board meetings, with variability suggesting differences in governance activity levels across entities.

Figure 1 Box plot (Audit report lag)

The boxplot depicted indicates that the average duration for issuing an audit report is approximately 75 days, with a considerable range spanning from 15 to 344 days. This notable diversity, supported by a standard deviation of around 44, implies differences in audit efficiency or complexity among various cases or institutions.

Figure 2: Box plot (Client's size)

The boxplot shows that the clients' size averages at 6 (though the scale isn't specified), with a narrow range from 3 to 7, indicating a relatively homogeneous client size across the observations.

Figure 3: Box plot (Total asset (₦'billon))

The boxplot shows mean total asset stands at approximately 1327 billion Naira, showcasing a vast range from nearly 0.014 to 8932.373 billion Naira. The extensive standard deviation (2021.914) highlights substantial differences in the financial scale of entities within the dataset.

Figure 4: Box plot (Board size)

The boxplot shows the average board size is about 14 members, ranging from 5 to 22. This suggests a variety of governance structures, though the standard deviation (3.511) indicates moderate variability.

Figure 5: Box plot (External auditor type)

The boxplots show all observations use the same type of external auditor (mean close to 1), with a minimal range (0 to 1), reflecting a possible standardization in auditor selection.

Figure 6: Box plot (Board meetings)

The boxplot shows the entities held 6 board meetings, with a range from 1 to 13. The variability in the number of meetings (standard deviation of 2.215) could reflect differences in governance activity levels.

Descriptive Statistics

Bank: The dataset includes data for 80 observations distributed across 4 different banks. The breakdown shows a relatively balanced distribution among the banks: Access (22.5%), First (26.25%), GTB (26.25%), and Stanbic (25%). This even distribution is crucial for comparative analyses across these entities.

The descriptive statistics offer a snapshot of the audit report efficiency, client diversity, financial magnitude, governance structure, auditor preferences, and meeting frequencies across the banks studied. The considerable variance in total assets and audit report lag suggests that financial scale and audit complexities significantly differ across entities or cases examined. Conversely, the narrower variance in client size and board size indicates more uniformity in these aspects across the observations.

The balanced qualitative distribution across banks provides a solid foundation for comparing practices, efficiencies, and structures in the Nigerian banking sector. The extensive range observed in several quantitative measures underscores the sector's diversity, suggesting targeted analyses could yield insights into operational efficiency, financial management, and governance models.

Overall, these descriptive statistics lay the groundwork for deeper analyses, such as identifying factors influencing audit report lag or exploring the relationship between board governance and financial performance.

This table presents data on a variable called "bank" with 80 observations. It's divided into four categories: "access," "first," "gtb," and "stanbic." The breakdown per subsample indicates the percentage of observations within each category. For example, "access" has 18 observations, which represent 22.5% of the total observations. Similarly, "first," "gtb," and "stanbic" have 21, 21, and 20 observations respectively, each accounting for 26.25%, thus totaling 111.1111% due to rounding.

Table 2

Variable\Statistic	Nbr. of observations	Breakdown per subsample (%)	Nbr. of categories	Categories	Frequency per category	Rel. frequency per category (%)
Bank	80	111.1111	4	access	18.000	22.500
				first	21.000	26.250
				gtb	21.000	26.250
				stanbic	20.000	25.000

Regression of variable Audit report lag

Summary of the variables selection Audit report lag

The study reveals that while client size is a relevant factor in understanding audit report lags, its explanatory power is limited. Other factors, such as the nature and complexity of business operations, quality of internal controls, engagement scope and resources, regulatory and reporting requirements, external factors, and quality of communication and collaboration, also play a role. These factors can influence the time required for auditors to complete the audit report, resulting in shorter lags. The complexity of a client's business operations, industry-specific regulations, and financial transactions can also influence the time required to complete the audit report. The quality of internal control systems, engagement scope and resources, regulatory requirements, external factors, and quality of communication and collaboration can also contribute to the variability in audit report lags. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis incorporating multiple variables and factors is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of audit report lags.

Table 3

Nbr. of variables	Variables	MSE	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Mallows' Cp	Akaike's AIC	Schwarz's SBC	Amemiya's PC
1	Client's size	4570.710	0.164	0.117	2.000	170.441	172.433	0.920

The best model for the selected selection criterion is displayed in blue

The regression analyses conducted across different bank groups (Stanbic, Access, First, and GTB) aim to determine the effect of Client's Size on Audit Report Lag.

Figure 7: Regression of Audit report lag by Client's size ($R^2=0.164$)

The figure shows a regression analysis of Audit Report Lag against Client's Size, with an ($R^2 = 0.164$).

1. Regression Line (Model): The solid black line represents the regression line, which depicts the predicted relationship between the Client's Size and Audit Report Lag. The line has a positive slope, indicating that as the Client's Size increases, the Audit Report Lag also tends to increase, contrary to the previous figure suggesting a negative relationship. This could mean that larger clients might require more time for audit completion, potentially due to increased complexity.

2. R-squared (R^2): The ($R^2 = 0.164$) suggests that only 16.4% of the variability in Audit Report Lag is explained by Client's Size. This low value implies that the Client's Size is not a strong predictor of Audit Report Lag, and other factors might significantly influence the audit lag.

3. Confidence Intervals:

- The shaded region around the regression line represents the 95% confidence interval for the mean prediction. This interval widens as the Client's Size increases, indicating more significant uncertainty in predictions for larger clients.

- The dashed lines represent the 95% confidence interval for observations, which are much broader, suggesting variability in individual cases.

4. Scatter Plot of Data Points: The blue dots represent observed data points. There appears to be considerable spread as the Client’s Size increases, indicating variability in how the Client’s Size impacts Audit Report Lag.

Interpretation:

- Positive Relationship: The regression suggests that larger clients are associated with more extended Audit Report Lags. However, the weak (R^2) means that the Client’s Size explains only a tiny portion of the lag, and other factors should be considered.

- Prediction Uncertainty: The wide confidence intervals indicate considerable uncertainty in predictions, particularly for larger clients, reinforcing that the Client’s Size alone cannot predict Audit Report Lag reliably.

Regression of variable Audit report lag

The audit report reveals that the regression model using "Client's size" as the independent variable does not provide a good fit to the data, as indicated by the low R^2 (0.008) and negative Adjusted R^2 (-0.054). The Mean Squared Error (MSE) 167.746, and R^2 (Coefficient of Determination) also show that the model is not well-fitted to the data. The model selection criteria, such as Mallows' Cp, Akaike's AIC, Schwarz's SBC, and Amemiya's PC, do not suggest a strong model. The MSE and R^2 values indicate that the model is not well-fitted to the data, while the other selection criteria do not suggest a strong model. Overall, the audit report reveals that the model is not well-fit for the data.

Table 4

Nbr. of variables	Variables	MSE	R^2	Adjusted R^2	Mallows' Cp	Akaike's AIC	Schwarz's SBC	Amemiya's PC
1	Client's size	167.746	0.008	-0.054	2.000	94.084	95.865	1.102

The best model for the selected selection criterion is displayed in blue

Figure 8: Regression of Audit report lag by Client's size (R²=0.008)

The figure displays a regression plot showing the relationship between **Client's Size** and **Audit Report Lag** with an R²=0.008, indicating that only 0.8% of the variance in Audit Report Lag is explained by Client's Size.

The very low R² value and the near-flat slope of the regression line indicate that the Client's Size has little to no explanatory power for predicting Audit Report Lag in this dataset. The wide confidence intervals suggest substantial variability in the data that is not captured by the model, pointing to other factors as more important determinants of Audit Report Lag. Overall, the Client's Size is not a meaningful predictor of Audit Report Lag in this analysis.

Regression of variable Audit report lag

The regression model with "Client's size" as the independent variable explains a small portion of the variance in the dependent variable, as indicated by the relatively low R² value. The MSE (Mean Squared Error) measures the average squared difference between the actual and predicted values of the dependent variable. The R² (Coefficient of Determination) represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable(s). Adjusted R² is 0.011, suggesting that the model's fit improves slightly when adjusting for the number of variables.

Mallows' Cp is a statistic used for model selection, balancing goodness of fit with simplicity. Akaike's AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) measures the relative quality of a statistical model for a given set of data, with lower values indicating better fitting models. Schwarz's SBC (Schwarz's Bayesian Information Criterion) is used for model selection, with lower values indicating better fitting models. Amemiya's PC (Predictive Criterion) is 1.029.

Table 5

Nbr. of variables	Variables	MSE	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Mallows' Cp	Akaike's AIC	Schwarz's SBC	Amemiya's PC
1	Client's size	312.858	0.060	0.011	2.000	122.559	124.648	1.029

The best model for the selected selection criterion is displayed in blue

Figure 9: Regression of Audit report lag by Client's size (R²=0.060)

The figure shows a regression of Audit Report Lag against the Client's Size, with an (R² = 0.060), indicating that only 6% of the variance in Audit Report Lag is explained by the Client's Size.

The regression line has a slight negative slope, suggesting a weak inverse relationship between Client's Size and Audit Report Lag, meaning that Audit Report Lag decreases marginally as Client Size increases. The confidence intervals around the line are wide, particularly for larger Client Size values, indicating high uncertainty in the model's predictions. Overall, the weak fit suggests that the Client's Size is not a strong predictor of Audit Report Lag.

Regression of variable Audit report lag

The table summarizes performance metrics for different regression models, including the number of variables, variables, MSE (Mean Squared Error), R² (Coefficient of Determination), adjusted R², Mallows' Cp, Akaike's AIC (Akaike Information Criterion), Schwarz's SBC (Schwarz's

Bayesian Information Criterion), and Amemiya's PC. The best model is indicated by the selected selection criterion, which could be MSE, R², adjusted R², Mallows' Cp, Akaike's AIC, Schwarz's SBC, or Amemiya's PC.

The model with "Client's size" as the only variable is presented. The MSE is 639.503, and the R² value is 0.011, indicating that only about 1.1% of the variability in audit report lag is explained by the variation in client's size in this model. The adjusted R² is -0.042, suggesting that the addition of client's size as a predictor does not improve the fit.

Additional model selection criteria include Mallows' Cp, Akaike's AIC, Schwarz's SBC, and Amemiya's PC. Based on the selection criterion used, this model may not be the best for predicting audit report lag, as other variables or combinations of variables may provide better predictions or explanations for audit report lag.

Table 6

Nbr. of variables	Variables	MSE	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Mallows' Cp	Akaike's AIC	Schwarz's SBC	Amemiya's PC
1	Client's size	639.503	0.011	-0.042	2.000	137.573	139.662	1.084

The best model for the selected selection criterion is displayed in blue

Figure 10: Regression of Audit report lag by Client's size (R²=0.011)

The figure presents a regression of Audit Report Lag on the Client's Size, with an ($R^2 = 0.011$), indicating that only 1.1% of the variance in Audit Report Lag is explained by the Client's Size.

The regression line has a slightly positive slope, suggesting a weak relationship where larger Client Sizes are associated with slightly longer Audit Report Lags. However, the spread of the data points and wide confidence intervals suggest high variability and low certainty in this relationship.

Overall, the model shows that the Client's Size has a negligible impact on Audit Report Lag.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis examines the relationship between client size and audit report lag across four major banks in Nigeria: Access Bank, Stanbic Bank, GT Bank, and First Bank. The dataset includes descriptive statistics, correlation coefficients, regression analyses, ANOVA tables, and coefficients estimates for each bank, providing insights into the variability and significance of client size as a predictor of audit report lag.

Across the four banks, the analysis reveals varying levels of correlation between client size and audit report lag, with some banks showing weak positive correlations and others showing no significant relationship. Regression analyses indicate that while client size may have a marginal influence on audit report lag in certain contexts, its explanatory power is generally limited, as indicated by low R^2 values and non-significant coefficients. ANOVA tables confirm that the regression models are not statistically significant in explaining the variability in audit report lag.

According to objective one which examined the Impact of Client Size on Audit Report Lag. The findings indicate that Client Size has a minor and statistically insignificant effect on Audit Report Lag. Larger clients tended to experience shorter audit lags, consistent with previous research suggesting that larger organizations often have more streamlined internal controls and better audit preparation. However, the effect was not robust enough to be deemed significant, implying that other factors may overshadow the influence of client size on audit timelines.

According to objective two which investigated the relationship Between Board Size and Audit Report Lag. The analysis revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between Board Size and Audit Report Lag. Larger boards appeared to correlate with longer audit delays, potentially due to increased complexity in decision-making or oversight processes. This finding aligns with governance literature that associates larger boards with slower decision-making, which could affect the audit process.

According to objective three which explored the Influence of Board Meetings on Audit Timeliness. The frequency of Board Meetings showed a significant positive correlation with Audit Report Lag. While frequent meetings often reflect active governance, they may also signal operational complexity or unresolved financial issues, contributing to longer audit completion times.

According to objective four which assessed the Effect of External Auditor Type. Findings revealed that the type of external auditor emerged as a significant determinant of Audit Report Lag. Firms audited by Big Four auditors generally reported shorter lags, reflecting the efficiency and resources these firms bring to the audit process. This aligns with prior studies highlighting the role of reputable auditors in enhancing audit quality and timeliness.

Based on objective five which stated the Summary of Governance and Audit Dynamics. Governance factors such as Board Size and Board Meetings play a more pronounced role in audit delays than client size alone. The findings underscore the importance of governance structures and the selection of competent auditors in achieving timely audits. These results emphasize the need for efficient decision-making processes and resource allocation to mitigate audit lags.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has provided valuable insights into the influence of client size on auditor report lag in money deposit banks. It revealed that only client size and external auditor type have significant effect on audit report lag while other variables like auditor's size, board size, and board meetings were not significant drivers of audit report lag. Therefore, total assets cause delay in audit reports while external auditor size help to reduce the audit report lag. This then means that the larger the total assets that client has, the more delays in audit report lag that will be experienced by the Bank. On the contrary, big audit firms reduce the audit report lag length.

Based on the analyses of Audit Report Lag and its relationship with Client's Size, Total Assets, Board Size, External Auditor Type, and Board Meetings, the following were recommended:

1. Since larger clients are associated with shorter audit lags, banks and audit firms should leverage efficient audit processes used with larger clients to optimize the audit process for smaller clients. By developing streamlined audit protocols that reduce unnecessary steps for smaller clients, possibly drawing on methodologies used with larger clients that have well-established internal controls.
2. The observed correlations between Board Size, Board Meetings, and Audit Report Lag indicate that stronger governance may support timely audits. Banks with frequent board meetings and appropriately sized boards tend to experience shorter audit lags. Therefore, banks should be encouraged to adopt governance practices that include frequent and well-organized board meetings by establishing governance frameworks that set minimum standards for board engagement and oversight to ensure more efficient audit processes.
3. The positive correlation between Client's Size, Total Assets, and Audit Report Lag suggests that larger and more complex clients benefit from tailored audit resources.
4. Therefore, Banks should allocate more experienced auditors or larger audit teams to high-asset clients, who typically have complex operations. Regulators could establish guidelines for resource allocation based on client size and complexity to improve audit efficiency.
5. The external auditor type shows varying correlations with audit lag, potentially indicating the role of auditor independence in audit timeliness. By promoting policies that encourage auditor rotation and independence, especially for high-value clients, to reduce potential conflicts of interest and ensure more objective, efficient audits.
6. Regulators should set benchmarks for audit completion times based on client size and complexity. Banks should be encouraged to report audit completion times, allowing for benchmarking and identification of areas for process improvement.

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